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O'ZARO HAMKORLIGI MASALALARI

XALQARO ILMIY-AMALIY KONFERENSIYA

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PRINCIPLES OF ACHIEVING FLUENCY BY TEACHING COMMUNICATIVE GRAMMAR

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Abstract: This article is about methods of formation of communicative speech of non-philology students in higher education. The structure, model, of the formation of communicative competence has been developed, it is based on the principles of activity, consistency, taking into account the educational and social experience of students, interactive methods of teaching, and consists of components: goal setting, organizational-methodological, effective assessment .

Key words: transfer, solid learning, psychologically, communicative lexicon, consciousness, visuality, interferential errors

In the most general form, acquisition can be defined as the process of receiving acquired knowledge, processing its meaning, retaining it, and applying it to new situations that require solving practical and theoretical problems. For example, mastering the grammatical rules of a foreign language means the ability to express thoughts in a foreign language. "This is the process of solid learning is the central part of the educational process. This is a very difficult process psychologically. They are never related to memory or the power of memory, but include the ability to perceive, understand, memorize and master material, use it freely in different situations, use it freely in different situations, apply it in different ways, and so on. ". At the same time, it is emphasized that new knowledge, skills and actions are not "transferred from head to head" in a ready form, they must be included in the personal experience of a person, they must be formed by the subject of training.

According to M.A. Qurbanova, it is very important to take into account the age and psychological state of learners in teaching a foreign language. Special attention should be paid to this, especially when teaching foreign languages to students. In the decisions of our country's president, attention was paid to this issue, that is, grammatical material is not provided to the first students when teaching a foreign language. Sometimes people describe grammar as the "rules" of language. But, people first made sounds, and then created words, phrases and sentences, creating a language. However, in many sources, grammar is defined as the rules that make up the structure of a language. Students find it difficult to master the rules and therefore get bored. Interestingly, language grammar seems to be a difficult area to master, even for adults. According to the author, in fact, it is not. It is well known that the ways of presenting grammar should be simplified and

made interesting. It is natural that grammar rules seem boring to students. Therefore, it is desirable that the grammatical material presented to students should be interesting, understandable and enjoyable.

F. Nazarova emphasized that in the process of learning a foreign language, many are limited to learning to speak or read. But they should understand that communicative grammar and communicative lexicon are also important for the practice of oral speech. Understanding the word form, combining it with other words to form sentences that represent a complete thought, as well as listening and reading the thought, requires the acquisition of grammatical skills and abilities.

The presentation of language material in the formation of students' interference competence is based on the following principles:

1. The principle of relying on the mother tongue. In this case, students rely on their mother tongue while learning the first foreign language, and on the skills of both the mother tongue and the first foreign language when acquiring the second foreign language.

2. The principle of communicative orientation of education. The basis of the communicative approach in the teaching of science aims to direct the knowledge acquired in the presentation and strengthening of all grammatical and phonetic materials to be used in the process of communication.

3. The principle of differentiated education. This principle envisages teaching taking into account the individual characteristics of the student in the process of mastering the subject.

4. The principle of consciousness. This assumes that every topic and language material presented is fully understood by the students. Based on this principle, by explaining the differences between the studied language and the native language, it is possible to achieve conscious elimination of errors.

5. The principle of visuality. It means that each topic should be presented with visual aids and tools. Because students remember events they saw for a long time than what they heard.

6. The principle of consistency in the presentation of language material. Language materials show that students' age, level of knowledge, and exercises should be presented sequentially, from easy to difficult.

7. The principle of mastering the types of speech activity as a whole. This includes strengthening language materials, including phonetics, grammar and lexicon, together with reading, speaking, listening comprehension and writing skills, which are types of speech activities.

8. The principle of taking into account grammatical and phonetic difficulties in the interaction between the studied language and the mother tongue.

Linguistic interference is a normative difference of one language caused by the influence of another language, and it directly depends on language levels. In particular, it can be observed that some cases related to phonetic interference lead to errors related to the meaning of the word. For example, the pronunciation of the word "hokim" in Uzbek as "khakim" in Russian creates a lexical error, because the

word "khakim" is used in the sense of doctor in Uzbek. In the interaction of languages, there are various forms of such situations.

In learning a language, it is important not only to speak, but also to understand the language. Interferential errors also have a negative impact on speech understanding. Based on this aspect, that is, based on the level of understanding of speech in the studied language, interference can be divided into the following types: 1) interference that makes understanding difficult; 2) interference that distorts understanding; 3) interference that allows understanding. These types of interference are also called strong, medium and weak interference.

Internal interference refers to the situation of incorrect use of the skills and competences acquired later in the language itself under the influence of the skills that were initially formed. Yu. Tregubova emphasizes that many spelling errors in the speech of learners are considered an important factor in the occurrence of internal interference. For example, in English, the plural form of nouns is mainly formed by adding the suffix -s to the singular noun (place - places). However, the plural form of some nouns (man - men, foot - feet, woman - women) is formed by changing the stem due to internal inflections.

In order to know what kind of subject a foreign language is, it is necessary to study its purpose and conditions. The relationship between the conditions and the goal is that the conditions are primary to the goal, and the goal is derived from it.

What is meant by a condition that is a concept in linguodidactics. By conditions, we take into account the following linguodidactic concept:

1. Type of educational institution.
2. Psychological age of the student.
3. Language experience of students. (knowledge, skill, qualification).
4. Time allocated to language learning.

In all educational institutions, the goal is to teach 4 types of speech activities. As a final result of education based on the competence approach, students should learn to exchange information in English. A communicator or a receptive student demonstrates speech competence when performing or perceiving speech, and can achieve the status of a communicator only if he has mastered small grammatical, lexical, pronunciation, and spelling skills. Communicative purpose represents free speech activity. In our era of globalization, the general goal of teaching English is to contribute to the education and development of a highly spiritual person.

In conclusion, building communicative competence is an interesting but not easy task. The ability to speak and create develops gradually: knowledge is accumulated, general culture, literacy, the ability to express one's thoughts grows, the personality is educated and developed. Children themselves do not learn to think, reflect, think, create, they need to be taught gradually, skillfully, experimentally. Technologies presented in the work allow to achieve this result.

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CHET TILINI MAHSUS MAQSADLARDA O'RGANUVCHILARGA FANNI O'QITISHNING ZAMONAVIY TEXNOLOGIYALARI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada nofilologik yo'nalishlarda o'qiydigan talabalarga mutaxassislikka doir bo'lgan matnlarni ingliz tilida o'qitish metodlari hamda zamonaviy texnologiyalar yordamida o'rgatish masalalari bayon etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: English for Specific Purposes (ESP), Multilevel, ko'p darajali ingliz tilini o'qitish, Maxsus maqsadlarda ingliz tili o'rganish va o'qitish, Transport vositalari muhandisligi ta'lim yo'nalishi, usul, texnika, metod, kompetensiya, kommunikativ malaka.

Kirish

Jadal suratlarda rivojlanayotgan davrda xorijiy tillarni, xususan ingliz tilini turli maqsadlarda, ya'ni turli sohalarda ta'lim olayotgan o'quvchi va talabarga o'rgatish hamda o'quv uslubiy ta'minotini ishlab chiqish muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. XX asrning 60 - yillaridan boshlab ESP, maxsus maqsadlarda ingliz tili o'rganish, birinchi marta ingliz tilini chet tili sifatida o'rgatishning alohida yo'nalishi sifatida e'tirof etilganligi, keyinchalik shu doirada o'qitishning bu jihati sezilarli darajada rivojlanishini kuzatish mumkin. Shu tufayli mahsus maqsadlarda ingliz tilini o'qitish etakchi o'rinni egalladi.

Materiallar va metodlar